

possible *X. fastidiosa* vectors in southern Mediterranean shores. There were 1,757 Auchenorrhyncha results in 2017 and 2019 from collections in forests, cultivated or abandoned orchards or Mediterranean scrub of Djebel Boukornine, Djebel Chitana, Djebel Khroufa, and Djebel Abderahman. *Quercus suber* and *Q. faginea*, *Pinus halepensis*, *Pistacia lentiscus* and *Myrtus communis* dominate the plant associations. Collections by sweeping nets and mouth aspirators from cultivated and uncultivated orchards in the sandy, weedy environments near olive, peach, citrus, apricot, and ornamental trees were initiated in the regions of Bizerte, Béja, Tunis, Nabeul, Zaghuan, and in the park of Dar Chichou and Lac Ichkeul. Most of the collected species, 35%, belong to Cicadellidae. *Exitianus capicola* (Deltocephalid) was the most abundant species in olive, peach and apricot orchards. *Balclutha* spp. and *Cicadulina bipunctata* were abundant in citrus and olive orchards. The planthoppers (Fulgoroidea) were prevalent in forests with *Toya propinqua* and *Sogatella kolophon* the most abundant Fulgoromorpha species. The spittlebugs *P. spumarius* and *N. campestris* live in Djebel Chitana of Bizerte, in the park of Dar Chichou and Lac Ichkeul, and near the olive and citrus orchards of Zaghuan, Korbous and Kairouan. Thereby, in case of unwanted *Xylella* introduction, we expect the bacterium to invade the country given the presence of vectors, susceptible plants and favourable climate.

Taxonomy and re-description of species within the genus *Philaenus*

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Abstract: *Philaenus spumarius* (Hemiptera: Aphrophoridae) is the efficient vector of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Italy and is found mixed with *P. tessellatus* and *P. maghresinus* in Tunisia.

This approach studied *Philaenus* collected by sweep net in Italy (Puglia) and in Tunisia to differentiate the three Tunisian species. Tunisian material originates from Ben Arous, Nabeul, Bizerte, Béja, Jendouba, Kairouan in *Pinus* and *Quercus* forests and also on *Pistacia* or *Asphodelus* understory, in olive, peach, citrus orchards and grapevines, and on natural herbs or weeds.

Apart from the interest in describing Tunisian fauna of Hemiptera, we need a clear taxonomic contribution based on the study of male genitalia for the identification of the 10 *Philaenus* species. The need arises because one of the species (*spumarius*) is a highly efficient vector of *Xylella fastidiosa*: a quarantine plant pathogenic bacterium threatening plant health in the Mediterranean basin. The correct specific identification will allow quantitative sampling and consequent effective control measures and strategy building.

The only comparative paper considers eight species and is useful for skilled researchers but less accessible for phytosanitary services or other students starting comparative *Philaenus* identification.

Here we focus and fully illustrate the morphological differences in male genitalia, targeting the shapes of: 1) aedeagus base (phallobase) from side and posterior view; 2) aedeagus shaft from side and posterior view; 3) number, shape, size, and points of insertion of aedeagal processes (projections); 4) endophallus window shape; and 5) anal tube in dorsal view of *P. spumarius*, *P. tessellatus*, and *P. maghresinus*.

Given the opportunity to discriminate the three taxa we found that *P. tessellatus* occurs in the northeast and west of Tunisia and is the most abundant species in the prospected regions. Furthermore, *P. spumarius* and *P. maghresinus* seem to occur associated in a limited area only in one locality in the north-east of Tunisia.

Potential insect vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Montenegro

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Abstract: As olive is the most widespread fruit tree in Montenegro, eventual detection of the bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* would cause great economic losses, besides implying the implementation of a permanent monitoring campaign. This is especially due to the importance of early detection of the bacteria as well as its vector(s) for the timely implementation of control measures to prevent it spreading. Given the significance of the vectors in the transmission of *X. fastidiosa* and the limited information about their presence in Montenegro, a study was undertaken to determine the species of Auchenorrhyncha (Cicadomorpha) present in olive groves on the Montenegrin coast. During 2018, insects were collected using sweep net sampling at three locations in the area of Valdanos and two locations in the area of Radanovići (Sampling was carried out on weeds, twice in the area of Valdanos (late May and late October) and once in the area of Radanovići (early September)). The collected insects were preserved in 96% alcohol until determination. Insect identification was performed on the basis of the morphological characteristics of the species. Sixteen Auchenorrhyncha species were identified of which 12 belong to the Cicadomorpha, three to the Aproclyptidae and nine to the Cicadellidae families. In all three locations in the area of Valdanos the most prevalent was *Philaenus spumarius* L. (main vector of *X. fastidiosa* in Europe) while *Lepyronia coleoptrata* (L.) was mainly collected in the area of Radanovići (.

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Phenology and host-plant selection of *Philaenus spumarius* in vineyards of north-western Italy

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Abstract: In order to contribute to the risk assessment of *Xylella fastidiosa* in vineyards, surveys of *Philaenus spumarius* were carried out in north-western Italy. A vineyard in Asti was sampled in 2016 and 2017. It was selected because of the ecological complexity of the site including grapevine rows, and herbaceous cover within and around the rows and broadleaved trees/shrubs surrounding the vineyard, as alternative hosts for the spittlebug adults. Nymphs and adults were sampled every 10 and 15 days, respectively, from the beginning of March until the beginning of December in both years. Nymphs were counted and their host plant identified, in herbaceous cover of vineyard headlands and inter-rows. Adults were sampled from three vegetation compartments of the vineyard: i) grapevine plants; ii) herbaceous vegetation (headlands and inter-rows); and iii) shrubs, trees and other spontaneous woody plants. Herbaceous cover was visually inspected for foam and nymphs, and each nymph was assigned to a life stage. Sampling of nymphs was done in randomly selected areas of 0.25 m², delimited by a rectangular frame. Adults were collected by sweeping net, counted, sexed, identified and immediately released. All samplings were conservative. Population dynamics and phenology, with respect to chronological and physiological time, were described for both nymphs and adults. Host plant selection of nymphs and vegetation compartments of adults are reported all over the two years. Five more vineyards in the Piedmont Region, besides the one in Asti, were inspected in 2018 using the same methodology, although surveys were carried out only three times in the season. The first survey was conducted in April, at the time of nymph population peak. The second and third surveys were aimed at sampling adults in June and September. Population abundance and host plant selection by nymphs, as well as population abundance and vegetation compartments of adults are reported.

Assessment of the genetic diversity in populations of *Philaenus spumarius* collected from different areas